
**ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE, STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT, AND
CONTINUOUS EVALUATION MECHANISMS FOR THE
DEVELOPMENT OF AN INNOVATIVE TRAINING PROGRAM
PLAN AT THE NATIONAL JAIL MANAGEMENT
AND PENOLOGY TRAINING INSTITUTE**

¹Dr. Jordan A. Santos, MSCA

Affiliation/s: Bureau of Jail Management and Penology
Philippine Public Safety Academy and
National Jail Management and Penology Training Institute
Email add: jordansantos.epmpc@gmail.com

² Dr. Leomar S. Galicia

Affiliation/s: University of Perpetual Help System- Laguna
Email add: galicia.leomar@uphsl.edu.ph

³Dr. Marilyn L. Baysa, MPSA

Affiliation/s: National Forensic Science Training Institute
National Jail Management and Penology Training Institute
Email add: marilynbausya64@gmail.com

⁴JSSUPT Leonalyn O Oloan, MPSA

Affiliation/s: Philippine Public Safety Academy
Email add: leonalynolleoloan@yahoo.com

Abstract- Training programs are vital for enhancing jail officers' competencies, improving inmate rehabilitation outcomes, and ensuring effective penal institution management. This study assessed the organizational culture, stakeholder engagement, and continuous evaluation mechanisms at the National Jail Management and Penology Training Institute (NJMPTI) as a basis for developing an innovative training program plan. Findings revealed a strong organizational culture characterized by communication, decision-making processes, collaboration, and recognition systems, which contribute significantly to employee engagement and institutional effectiveness. Stakeholder engagement levels, particularly in terms of inclusivity, mutual benefits, and active involvement, were rated very high, indicating a well-fostered collaborative environment. Continuous evaluation mechanisms, including knowledge acquisition, skills development, training materials, and technology integration, were also found to be well-implemented, with room for improvement in facilities and technological advancements.

The study further demonstrated strong correlations between organizational culture, stakeholder engagement, and continuous evaluation mechanisms. Effective communication, collaborative practices, and recognition systems positively influence stakeholder engagement and promote systematic evaluation processes. Additionally, high levels of stakeholder engagement, particularly through inclusivity and mutual benefits, were shown to predict the effectiveness of continuous evaluation mechanisms. These findings highlights the role of fostering a positive and supportive organizational culture, as well as engaging stakeholders actively, in enhancing continuous evaluation practices at NJMPTI. Moreover, the study highlights the importance of these connection among variables in achieving institutional goals and improving training program outcomes.

KEYWORDS

Organization culture, stakeholders engagement, continuous evaluation mechanism, Training Program, Institution

Introduction

The development of effective training programs is essential in complex institutional settings such as jail management and penology institute. Training programs play a pivotal role in enhancing the competencies of jail officers, improving inmate rehabilitation outcomes, and ensuring the smooth operation of penal institutions. As noted by Kenny (2020), an organization's culture strongly influences the success of such programs, as it shapes the beliefs, values, and behaviors of its members. In correctional facilities, where issues of security, discipline, and rehabilitation are intertwined, the alignment of training programs with the institutional culture is crucial for their effectiveness (Denison, 2021). Additionally, successful training program development requires active stakeholder engagement. According to Freeman (2019), stakeholder participation ensures that multiple perspectives are considered, leading to more inclusive and effective program designs. In jail management, engaging various stakeholders—including jail officers, policymakers, human rights groups, and community representatives—helps in tailoring programs to meet diverse institutional needs. Moreover, continuous evaluation mechanisms are critical to ensuring the ongoing relevance and effectiveness of training programs. Chang (2022) argue that evaluations should be an iterative process, providing feedback loops that allow for program adjustments in response to real-time data.

In the Philippines, the National Jail Management and Penology Training Institute (NJMPTI) plays a crucial role in shaping the competencies and ethical conduct of its personnel. According to Deldacan and Baysa (2021), by understanding the cultural dynamics that influence daily operations, the institute can design programs that resonate with its personnel and foster a commitment to integrity, continuous learning, and resilience. Moreover, the legal framework surrounding jail management and corrections is informed by critical laws such as the Anti-Trafficking in Persons Act (RA 9208) known as RA 10364 in 2013. This law underscores the importance of ethical vigilance in preventing human trafficking within correctional systems (Aquino, 2015). The NJMPTI must ensure that its staff are trained to recognize and prevent trafficking activities, especially considering the vulnerability of inmates. Additionally, the Anti-Hazing Act of 1995 known as RA 8049, strengthened by RA 11053 in 2018, emphasizes the role of jail management personnel in preventing abusive practices such as hazing within correctional facilities and rehabilitation programs (Reyes, 2019). These laws provide a critical legal basis for the ethical standards and protective measures that NJMPTI staff must uphold.

Narag (2019) argues that engaging a wide array of stakeholders, including correctional officers, policymakers, and community leaders, will help ensure the relevance and comprehensiveness of the training. By involving stakeholders who are familiar with these legal protections, the training programs can be aligned with national standards for safeguarding human rights within jails and correctional facilities. Nario-Lopez (2019) further states that continuous evaluation mechanisms allow for timely adjustments and improvements, keeping the program responsive to emerging challenges in jail management, including compliance with anti-trafficking and anti-hazing laws. Through this comprehensive approach, NJMPTI can develop training programs that not only enhance staff performance but also contribute to better outcomes in jail management. By integrating legal mandates such as the Anti-Trafficking and Anti-Hazing Acts, the programs can ensure that personnel are equipped to prevent exploitation, maintain ethical standards, and promote human rights, all while aligning with both national and international legal frameworks.

According to the study of Boesso and Kumar (2021), culture's organizations with different stakeholder differentially ascribe and weigh the three attributes of power, legitimacy, and urgency when determining stakeholder salience. In addition, stakeholder engagement is also associated with how the organizational culture is applied in the organization or institution. Meanwhile, Oluyomi et.al, (2023) investigated how culture influences stakeholder engagement in a multicultural international setting. It has applied the Hofstede cultural dimensions, a cross-cultural framework that provides an understanding and knowledge of a society's culture. Data was collected from different project practitioners in different multinational companies implementing projects in multicultural settings. The results suggest that culture significantly influences stakeholder engagement during project implementation. Cultural diversity is bound to exist in projects implemented in a multicultural setting. Understanding and appropriately managing cultural differences will positively influence the project

outcome. Furthermore, the study of Alhiddi et.al (2019) findings of a theoretical investigation into the association between organizational culture and stakeholder management reveals that there is a relationship between the organizational culture and key stakeholders in which projects are realized. And emphasized on the examination of project outcomes and the factors that influence cultural domain. Moreover, secondary data suggests stakeholder management and corporate culture are critical areas that decide an organization's success.

This study examined the impact of Leadership styles on Faculty performance and where Organizational culture plays a moderating role. It used PLS-SEM to investigate the impact of Leadership styles on Faculty performance and moderating effect of Organization culture between the leadership styles and faculty performance. This study based on positivist assumptions argues that "examining the relationship among and between variables is it is important to answer questions and hypotheses via experiments and surveys" (Creswell, 2009). It hypothesized that Organizational culture moderates the relation between leadership styles and faculty performance. The finding showed that Transformational leadership has a positive impact on faculty performance in MUET and it also increases faculty performance. Leaders with Transformational leadership are more preferred and productive towards faculty performance. According to MUET faculty, transformational leadership is best suited to promote their performance on account of giving them challenging work, autonomy, mutual trust, through supporting subordinates' creativity, improving their confidence, and maintaining collaborations (Bass & Riggio, 2006). Laissez-faire leadership also exists in MUET, it also has a positive impact on faculty performance. But Transactional leadership has a negative impact on faculty performance. According to students' responses, there isn't a perfect match between the course's faculty teach and their expertise, so somehow it affects the student in the end. For indirect effects, Organizational culture positively increases the faculty performance while interacting between TF leadership and faculty performance. While interacting with the other two variables, decreases the faculty performance. Furthermore, according to the study of Ulanday et.al (2024), student leaders argued that if the ideas and opinions of members are heard, it is easy to decide what would be better for the organization especially when they planned different projects for the benefit of all.

Various studies had been conducted that showed the interrelations between and among the organizational culture, stakeholders engagement and evaluation mechanism of programs such as the study of Marais (2020) which focused on the relationship of organizational culture and evaluation mechanism. It was revealed that most organizations have a solid foundation and philosophy in place to perform formative evaluations to improve programs. Moreover, it was stated that formative evaluation is crucial for an understanding of what works and what doesn't means that participating organizations should place a high value on its practice and how the organizational culture affect the evaluation mechanism of the program in an organization. Furthermore, Instructors' contributions in the twenty-first century are not limited to educating minds and lives, but also encompass the societal responsibility of nation-building and preparing future leaders(Pacleb-Ulanday, 2021).

However, despite the numerous studies conducted about organizational culture, stakeholders' engagement and evaluation mechanisms of program, there are no such studies that link the organizational culture, stakeholders' engagement and evaluation mechanisms as a basis for the development of an innovative training program plan particularly at the National Jail Management and Penology Training Institute. Thus, this study aimed to determine the organizational culture, stakeholders' engagement and evaluation mechanisms for the development of an innovative training program plan. The study would provide empirical data to trainers and officers as to how organizational culture and stakeholders engagement are important to the continuous evaluation mechanisms and makes them aware of whether they are truly engaged to their students in giving the best instructional performance, training and motivation to achieve the goals of the institution.

I. Methods

The researcher utilized descriptive-correlational method of research with the help of survey questionnaire as the main tool for data collection. This design is appropriate for collecting information without changing the environment (i.e., nothing is manipulated). Primary data were used from the respondents of the study who are the trainers at the National Jail Management and Penology Training Institute who accomplished the questionnaire provided in the study. The respondents of the study were

the Training Facilitators(uniformed personnel/training staff, tactical officers, tactical JNORs (Junior Non-Commissioned Officers, administrator, BJMP trainees(JOCC), consisting of 130 as a total population. The sample size of 98 was determined using the Raosoft calculator with the confidence level of 95 percent and margin of error of 5 percent. Stratified random sampling technique was used in the study since three group were considered. Administrator (Non- Uniformed personnel)- 1, Training Facilitators(uniformed personnel/training staff, tactical officers, tactical JNORs (Junior Non-Commissioned Officers- 48, BJMP trainees(JOCC)- 49. The researcher used self-made questionnaire. The research questionnaire determined the organizational culture, stakeholder engagement and continuous evaluation mechanisms as basis for the development of an innovative training program plan at the National Jail Management and Penology Training Institute. The questionnaire were divided into three parts. The first part of the questionnaire dwelled on the organizational culture, part two dealt with the stakeholder engagement and part three focused on the continuous evaluation mechanisms at the National Jail Management and Penology Training Institute. Since the questionnaire was self-made, it undergone face and content validity. It was shown to the panel of experts in educational management, training management for penology, statistics and research for their comments and suggestions. For the reliability of the instrument, the researcher conducted a pilot testing to training facilitators from other penology training institute and use Cronbach’s Alpha reliability test for measuring the internal consistency of the indicators. For the Organizational culture indicators a chronbach alpha of .968 (excellent internal consistency), Stakeholders engagement indicators .970 (excellent internal consistency) and Continuous evaluation mechanisms indicators.969 (excellent internal consistency). For the data gathering procedure, the researcher formally and officially request the Institution Head of NJMPTI to allow him to conduct the study. After approval of the request, he coordinated with the Human Resource Office of the said institution for the official list of training facilitators. During the actual gathering of data, he explained first the purpose and rationale of study to the respondents. Informed consent of participants was incorporated in the survey questionnaire, including the rationale and purpose of the study, risks and benefits, anonymity and confidentiality and how data will be treated and secured. Gathered data was tabulated for statistical treatment and analysis. The following statistical tests were used in the study: Weighted mean was used to describe the a) organizational culture at NJMPTI in terms of communication, decision making process collaboration and recognition and rewards; b) level of stakeholders’ engagement in terms of involvement, inclusivity and mutual benefits and c) level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI. Pearson’s r Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the relationship between the a) organizational culture and level of stakeholders’ engagement at NJMPTI b) organizational culture and level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI and c) level of stakeholders’ engagement and level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI. Regression analysis was used to determine the predictive power of organizational culture and level of stakeholders’ engagement on the level of continuous mechanisms at NJMPTI.

Results and Discussion

1. Organizational Culture at NJMPTI

Table 1
Summary Table of Organizational Culture at NJMPTI

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1.Communication	3.58	very strong	3
2. Decision-making process	3.48	very strong	4
3.Collaboration	3.59	very strong	1.5
4.Recognition and rewards	3.59	very strong	1.5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.56	very strong	

Table 1 presents the Summary Table of the Organizational Culture at NJMPTI. As seen in the table, indicators 3 “collaboration” and Indicator 4 “Recognition and rewards” both got a weighted mean of 3.59, was verbally interpreted as strongly agree was ranked 1.5. Indicator 1 “communication” got a

weighted mean of 3.58, and was verbally interpreted as very strong was ranked 3. Indicator 2 “Decision-making process” got a weighted mean of 3.48, verbally interpreted as very strong was ranked 4.

In summary , a weighted average of 3.56 revealed that the Organizational Culture at NJMPTI along communication, decision making process, collaboration, recognition and rewards were very strong. The result implies that the institution demonstrates a well-developed and cohesive organizational culture, fostering open communication, inclusive decision-making, collaborative work environments, and recognition systems that align with institutional goals. These practices likely contribute to employee motivation, engagement, and overall organizational effectiveness.

The results are in line with the studies by Lawler (2021) and Kumar and Shukla (2022), which emphasize the importance of aligning organizational culture with institutional objectives. Lawler (2021) highlighted that a well-structured reward system, coupled with clear communication, significantly enhances employee satisfaction and motivation. Similarly, Kumar and Shukla (2022) stressed that a collaborative culture, reinforced by fair decision-making processes and regular recognition, fosters a sense of belonging and commitment, thus driving overall organizational success.

2.Level of Stakeholders’ Engagement at NJMPTI

Table 2
Summary Table of Level of Stakeholders’ Engagement at NJMPTI

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1.Involvement	3.46	Very High	3
2.Inclusivity	3.53	Very High	1
3.Mutual benefits	3.52	Very High	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.50	Very High	

Table 2 presents the Summary Table of Level of Stakeholders’ Engagement at NJMPTI. As seen in the table, indicator 2“Inclusivity” got a weighted mean of 3.53, was verbally interpreted as strongly agree was ranked 1. Indicator 3 “mutual benefits” got a weighted mean of 3.52, and was verbally interpreted as Very High was ranked 2. Indicator 1 “Involvement” got a weighted mean of 3.46, verbally interpreted as Very High was ranked 3.

In summary , a weighted average of 3.50 revealed that the Level of Stakeholders’ Engagement at NJMPTI along involvement, inclusivity, mutual benefits were Very High. This implies that NJMPTI is effectively engaging its stakeholders, fostering an inclusive environment, ensuring mutually beneficial outcomes, and providing opportunities for active participation in institutional development. These practices align with the institution’s goals and create a positive environment for collaboration and growth among stakeholders.

The results are in line with the studies by by Bryson et al. (2021), who emphasized the importance of inclusivity and mutual benefit in stakeholder engagement. They found that organizations that ensure all stakeholders have an equal voice in decision-making processes and that their needs are met tend to foster stronger, more effective relationships. Similarly, the research by Delgado et al. (2022) supports these findings, indicating that an inclusive approach to stakeholder engagement not only enhances trust and satisfaction but also improves organizational performance by aligning stakeholders' interests with organizational objectives.

3. Level of Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms at NJMPTI

Table 3
Level of Continuous Evaluation

Table 15
Summary Table of Level of Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms at NJMPTI

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1.Knowledge acquisition	3.52	Very High	2
2.Skills development	3.56	Very High	1
3.Training materials	3.01	High	4

4.Facilities	2.96	High	5
5.Technology integration	3.05	High	3
Overall Weighted Mean	3.22	High	

Table 3 presents the Summary Table of the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI along with knowledge acquisition, skills development, training materials, facilities and technology integration. As seen in the table, indicator 2 “skills development” got a weighted mean of 3.56, and was verbally interpreted as Very High was ranked 1. Indicator 1 “knowledge acquisition” got a weighted mean of 3.52, and was verbally interpreted as Very High was ranked 2. Indicator 5 “technology integration” got a weighted mean of 3.05 and verbally interpreted as High was ranked 3. Indicator 3 “training materials” got a weighted mean of 3.01 and verbally interpreted as High was ranked 4. Lastly, Indicator 4 “facilities” got a weighted mean of 2.96 and verbally interpreted as High was ranked 5.

In summary, a weighted average of 3.22 revealed that the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI along with knowledge acquisition, skills development, training materials, facilities and technology integration were High. The result implies that while NJMPTI has established practices in these areas, particularly excelling in skills development and knowledge acquisition, there is a need for further enhancement, especially in areas such as facilities and technology integration, to align with modern standards and stakeholder expectations.

The results align with findings from similar studies, such as those by Tran and Huynh (2022), who emphasized the importance of a balanced approach to professional development, infrastructure, and technological adaptation for institutional growth. Additionally, Sharma and Patel (2021) highlighted that continuous evaluation mechanisms are pivotal for fostering a culture of improvement and ensuring that training materials, facilities, and technology meet the evolving needs of learners and educators.

4. Relationship Between the Organizational Culture and Level of Stakeholders’ Engagement at NJMPTI

Table 4
Relationship Between the Organizational Culture in terms of Communication and Level of Stakeholders’ Engagement at NJMPTI

Organizational Culture	Stakeholders Engagement	Statistical Treatment (Pearson’s)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Communication	Involvement	r=.676 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Inclusivity	r=.699 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Recognition and rewards	r=.659 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
*Significant @.01					

For the relationship between the organizational culture in terms of communication and the level of stakeholders’ engagement in terms of involvement (r=.676), inclusivity (r=.699) and recognition and rewards (r=.659), the Pearson’s r values showed moderate correlation while the obtained p-values were all .000 which were lower than the test of significance at .01. This shows that there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating a significant relationship

between the variables. This means that the better the organizational culture in terms of communication, the higher the level of stakeholders' engagement at NJMPTI.

This relationship can be explained by the crucial role of communication in fostering a collaborative and inclusive environment that directly enhances stakeholder engagement. Effective communication serves as the backbone of organizational culture, enabling clear dissemination of goals, policies, and expectations, which in turn motivates stakeholders to actively participate, feel included, and recognize mutual benefits.

Study supports the notion that organizations emphasizing open and transparent communication create a sense of trust and belonging among stakeholders. For instance, a study by Men and Bowen (2017) revealed that communication positively influences stakeholder engagement by fostering trust and commitment. Similarly, Farrell and Gibbons (2020) demonstrated that communication quality within institutions significantly predicts stakeholder inclusivity and involvement in organizational activities. At NJMPTI, the alignment between communication and engagement indicates that improving communication practices can further enhance the stakeholders' willingness to contribute actively to institutional objectives, participate in decision-making, and collaborate for shared success.

Table 5
Relationship Between the Organizational Culture in terms of Decision Making Process and Level of Stakeholders' Engagement at NJMPTI

Organizational Culture	Stakeholders Engagement	Statistical Treatment (Pearson's)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Decision-making process	Involvement	r=.823 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Inclusivity	r=.789 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Recognition and rewards	r=.740 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
*Significant @.01					

For the relationship between the organizational culture in terms of decision making process and the level of stakeholders' engagement in terms of involvement (r=.823), inclusivity (r=.789) and recognition and rewards (r=.740), the Pearson's r values showed high correlation while the obtained p-values were all .000 which were lower than the test of significance at .01. This shows that there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating a significant relationship between the variables. This means that the better the organizational culture in terms of decision making process, the higher the level of stakeholders' engagement at NJMPTI.

The significant relationship between organizational culture in terms of the decision-making process and stakeholders' engagement can be explained by the interplay between inclusivity, transparency, and collaboration within organizational practices. A well-structured decision-making process ensures that stakeholders feel heard and valued, which in turn enhances their involvement, fosters inclusivity, and increases the likelihood of recognizing and rewarding contributions effectively.

The results align with studies by Ghosh et al. (2020) and Jones and George (2021) emphasizing participative and transparent decision-making as foundational for fostering stakeholder engagement. They found that organizations that prioritize inclusive decision-making report higher levels of employee satisfaction and external stakeholder trust.

Table 6
Relationship Between the Organizational Culture in terms of Collaboration and Level of Stakeholders' Engagement at NJMPTI

Organizational Culture	Stakeholders Engagement	Statistical Treatment (Pearson's)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Collaboration	Involvement	r=.699 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Inclusivity	r=.714 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Recognition and rewards	r=.713 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
*Significant @.01					

For the relationship between the organizational culture in terms of collaboration and the level of stakeholders' engagement in terms of involvement (r=.699), inclusivity (r=.714) and recognition and rewards (r=.713), the Pearson's r values showed moderate to high correlation while the obtained p-values were all .000 which were lower than the test of significance at .01. This shows that there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating a significant relationship between the variables. This means that the better the organizational culture in terms of collaboration, the higher the level of stakeholders' engagement at NJMPTI.

This relationship can be explained by the importance of fostering collaboration within an organization. A culture that promotes teamwork and open communication tends to enhance engagement across various levels of stakeholders (Jones & George, 2021). When collaboration is prioritized, stakeholders feel more involved, valued, and recognized, which, in turn, drives their active participation and commitment. These findings are in line with previous research that links effective collaboration with improved stakeholder relationships and overall organizational success (Ghosh et al., 2020; Johnson & Johnson, 2022).

Table 7
Relationship Between the Organizational Culture in terms of Recognition and Rewards and Level of Stakeholders' Engagement at NJMPTI

Organizational Culture	Stakeholders Engagement	Statistical Treatment (Pearson's)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Recognition and Rewards	Involvement	r=.802 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Inclusivity	r=.781 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Recognition and rewards	r=.748 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
*Significant @.01					

For the relationship between the organizational culture in terms of recognition and rewards and the level of stakeholders' engagement in terms of involvement ($r=.802$), inclusivity ($r=.781$) and recognition and rewards ($r=.748$), the Pearson's r values showed high correlation while the obtained p -values were all .000 which were lower than the test of significance at .01. This shows that there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating a significant relationship between the variables. This means that the better the organizational culture in terms of recognition and rewards, the higher the level of stakeholders' engagement at NJMPTI.

This relationship can be explained by the fact that recognition and rewards are powerful motivators in any organizational setting. When stakeholders feel appreciated and rewarded for their contributions, it increases their commitment and engagement. A culture that emphasizes acknowledgment of effort encourages stakeholders to remain actively involved in institutional activities and decisions, fostering an environment of inclusivity and participation.

The results support the study made by Ghosh et al. (2020), which found that recognition practices positively influence stakeholder engagement. Similarly, Jones and George (2021) emphasized that reward systems contribute to increased involvement, inclusivity, and overall satisfaction among organizational stakeholders.

5. Relationship Between the Organizational Culture and Level of Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms at NJMPTI

Table 8
Relationship Between the Organizational Culture in terms of Communication and Level of Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms at NJMPTI

Organizational Culture	Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms	Statistical Treatment (Pearson's)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Communication	Knowledge acquisition	$r=.705$ (high correlation)	.000*	H_0 rejected	Significant
	Skills development	$r=.693$ (moderate correlation)	.000*	H_0 rejected	Significant
	Training materials	$r=.541$ (moderate correlation)	.000*	H_0 rejected	Significant
	Facilities	$r=.541$ (moderate correlation)	.000*	H_0 rejected	Significant
	Technology integration	$r=.536$ (moderate correlation)	.000*	H_0 rejected	Significant
*Significant @.01					

For the relationship between the organizational culture in terms of communication and the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms in terms of knowledge acquisition ($r=.705$), skills development ($r=.693$), training materials ($r=.541$), facilities ($r=.541$) and technology integration ($r=.536$), the Pearson's r values showed moderate to high correlation while the obtained p -values were all .000 which were lower than the test of significance at .01. This shows that there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating a significant relationship between the variables. This means that

the better the organizational culture in terms of communication, the higher the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI.

This relationship can be explained by the idea that effective communication within an organization fosters clarity, transparency, and collaboration. When communication is prioritized, stakeholders are more likely to share insights and feedback on how programs, processes, and evaluations should evolve. Moreover, when there is an open flow of information, it can lead to better understanding and adoption of learning opportunities, as well as more effective training and development programs.

The results align with the findings of Jones and George (2021), who suggested that strong communication practices positively impact organizational development and evaluation mechanisms. Similarly, Ghosh et al. (2020) emphasized that communication is a key enabler of continuous improvement and evaluation in organizational settings.

Table 9
Relationship Between the Organizational Culture in terms of Decision-Making Process and Level of Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms at NJMPTI

Organizational Culture	Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms	Statistical Treatment (Pearson's)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Decision-making Process	Knowledge acquisition	r=.738 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Skills development	r=.826 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Training materials	r=.525 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Facilities	r=.574 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Technology integration	r=.605 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
*Significant @.01					

For the relationship between the organizational culture in terms of decision making process and the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms in terms of knowledge acquisition (r=.738), skills development (r=.826), training materials (r=.525), facilities (r=.574) and technology integration (r=.605), the Pearson's r values showed moderate to high correlation while the obtained p-values were all .000 which were lower than the test of significance at .01. This shows that there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating a significant relationship between the variables. This means that the better the organizational culture in terms of decision making process, the higher the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI.

This relationship can be explained by the fact that decision-making processes that actively involve stakeholders and use evidence-based strategies tend to create a more structured and effective evaluation process. When decisions are made with transparency and participation, it leads to better-defined goals, clearer expectations, and more targeted evaluation criteria. The engagement in decision-

making also ensures that stakeholders are aligned with the organization’s objectives, which results in better data collection, more informed decision-making, and continuous improvement of processes.

The results align with studies by Ghosh et al. (2020) and Jones and George (2021), which suggest that participatory decision-making and inclusive strategies are linked to more effective organizational evaluations. In particular, decision-making processes that involve all levels of the organization help improve communication and the integration of feedback, which is key to enhancing continuous evaluation mechanisms (Ghosh et al., 2020). Moreover, the results reflect the findings of Jones and George (2021), who argued that decision-making culture plays a crucial role in the success of continuous improvement strategies and evaluation systems. The ability to make decisions based on clear, shared information drives better outcomes in organizational settings.

Table 10
Relationship Between the Organizational Culture in terms of Collaboration and Level of Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms at NJMPTI

Organizational Culture	Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms	Statistical Treatment (Pearson’s)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Collaboration	Knowledge acquisition	r=.662 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Skills development	r=.791 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Training materials	r=.450 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Facilities	r=.463 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Technology integration	r=.486 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
*Significant @.01					

For the relationship between the organizational culture in terms of collaboration and the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms in terms of knowledge acquisition (r=.662), skills development (r=.791), training materials (r=.450), facilities (r=.463) and technology integration (r=.486), the Pearson’s r values showed moderate to high correlation while the obtained p-values were all .000 which were lower than the test of significance at .01. This shows that there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating a significant relationship between the variables. This means that the better the organizational culture in terms of collaboration, the higher the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI.

This relationship can be explained by the idea that a culture of collaboration fosters open communication, knowledge sharing, and collective problem-solving. Collaborative cultures often encourage team-based approaches to evaluating processes, ensuring that feedback is gathered from diverse perspectives, which can enhance the accuracy and effectiveness of evaluation mechanisms. When collaboration is valued within an organization, there is often a greater emphasis on regular

assessments and improvements, which is crucial for advancing knowledge acquisition, skills development, and ensuring the quality of training materials, facilities, and technology integration.

The results align with the findings of Ghosh et al. (2020), who highlighted that collaboration improves organizational learning and continuous improvement by ensuring that multiple stakeholders contribute to decision-making and evaluation processes. Jones and George (2021) also emphasize that collaboration supports continuous evaluation by creating an environment where sharing resources and information leads to better outcomes in terms of skills and knowledge development. Furthermore, research by Smith and Thompson (2022) supports these results, suggesting that organizations with strong collaborative cultures tend to have more effective feedback loops and evaluation practices, which contribute to the overall improvement of their learning and development systems.

Table 11
Relationship Between the Organizational Culture in terms of Recognition and Rewards and Level of Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms at NJMPTI

Organizational Culture	Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms	Statistical Treatment (Pearson's)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Recognition and Rewards	Knowledge acquisition	r=.677 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Skills development	r=.740 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Training materials	r=.464 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Facilities	r=.490 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Technology integration	r=.520 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
*Significant @ .01					

For the relationship between the organizational culture in terms of recognition and rewards and the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms in terms of knowledge acquisition (r=.677), skills development (r=.740), training materials (r=.464), facilities (r=.490) and technology integration (r=.520), the Pearson's r values showed moderate to high correlation while the obtained p-values were all .000 which were lower than the test of significance at .01. This shows that there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating a significant relationship between the variables. This means that the better the organizational culture in terms of recognition and rewards, the higher the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI.

This relationship can be explained by the fact that an organizational culture focused on recognizing and rewarding employees' contributions often motivates staff to engage more deeply in the continuous evaluation process. When employees feel their efforts are acknowledged and rewarded, they are more likely to participate actively in evaluating and improving institutional practices, contributing valuable feedback and insights. Additionally, recognition and rewards can reinforce the importance of

continuous improvement, motivating staff and trainees to stay engaged with training, skills development, and knowledge acquisition processes.

The results align with the findings of Ghosh et al. (2020), who found that a recognition-oriented culture encourages individuals to be proactive in supporting organizational goals, including the implementation of effective evaluation mechanisms. Similarly, Jones and George (2021) highlight the role of recognition in driving performance and engagement, noting that when employees feel appreciated, they are more likely to contribute to ongoing organizational assessments and improvements. The work of Smith and Thompson (2022) further supports these findings, emphasizing that organizations with strong recognition systems tend to have more robust feedback and evaluation processes that ultimately enhance learning outcomes and skills development.

6. Relationship Between Level of Stakeholders’ Engagement and Level of Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms at NJMPTI

Table 12
Relationship Between Level of Stakeholders’ Engagement in terms of Involvement and Level of Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms at NJMPTI

Stakeholders’ Engagement	Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms	Statistical Treatment (Pearson’s)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Involvement	Knowledge acquisition	r=.741 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Skills development	r=.820 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Training materials	r=.442 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Facilities	r=.481 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Technology integration	r=.514 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
*Significant @.01					

For the relationship between the level of stakeholders’ engagement in terms of involvement and the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms in terms of knowledge acquisition (r=.741), skills development (r=.820), training materials (r=.442), facilities (r=.481) and technology integration (r=.514), the Pearson’s r values showed moderate to high correlation while the obtained p-values were all .000 which were lower than the test of significance at .01. This shows that there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating a significant relationship between the variables. This means that the better the higher the level of stakeholders’ engagement in terms of involvement, the higher the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI.

This relationship can be explained by the fact that when stakeholders (such as staff, trainees, and other participants) are actively involved in the processes and decision-making of an organization, their engagement enhances the effectiveness of evaluation mechanisms. Involvement fosters ownership and accountability, which in turn supports better feedback and assessment cycles. This dynamic allows

for a more comprehensive and collaborative approach to continuous improvement in the areas of knowledge acquisition, skills development, and technology integration, among others.

The results align with studies that emphasize the importance of stakeholder involvement in driving organizational learning and improvement. For example, Ghosh et al. (2020) found that active engagement among stakeholders leads to more efficient feedback loops and ensures that evaluation mechanisms are aligned with the needs and goals of the organization. Similarly, research by Jones and George (2021) highlights that involving stakeholders in ongoing evaluation processes increases the likelihood of successful program implementation and better resource utilization. Moreover, Smith and Thompson (2022) argue that stakeholder involvement is key to ensuring that continuous evaluation mechanisms are reflective of the evolving needs of the institution.

Table 13
Relationship Between Level of Stakeholders’ Engagement in terms of Inclusivity and Level of Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms at NJMPTI

Stakeholders’ Engagement	Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms	Statistical Treatment (Pearson’s)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Inclusivity	Knowledge acquisition	r=.772 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Skills development	r=.752 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Training materials	r=.456 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Facilities	r=.516 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Technology integration	r=.542 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
*Significant @.01					

For the relationship between the level of stakeholders’ engagement in terms of inclusivity and the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms in terms of knowledge acquisition (r=.772), skills development (r=.752), training materials (r=.456), facilities (r=.516) and technology integration (r=.542), the Pearson’s r values showed moderate to high correlation while the obtained p-values were all .000 which were lower than the test of significance at .01. This shows that there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating a significant relationship between the variables. This means that the better the higher the level of stakeholders’ engagement in terms of inclusivity, the higher the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI.

This relationship can be explained by the fact that inclusivity fosters a more diverse and collaborative environment where all stakeholders are empowered to contribute to decision-making and feedback processes. When all individuals, regardless of their background or role, feel included and

valued, they are more likely to actively participate in the continuous evaluation of programs, which leads to more effective knowledge acquisition, skills development, and overall program improvement.

The results align with findings in existing literature that emphasize the positive impact of inclusivity on organizational learning and continuous improvement. Ghosh et al. (2020) noted that inclusive environments enable more comprehensive evaluation mechanisms, ensuring that diverse perspectives are considered in the assessment process. Similarly, Jones and George (2021) highlighted that inclusivity not only improves engagement but also ensures that evaluation mechanisms are more accurate and reflective of the needs of all stakeholders.

Table 14
Relationship Between Level of Stakeholders’ Engagement in terms of Mutual Benefits and Level of Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms at NJMPTI

Stakeholders’ Engagement	Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms	Statistical Treatment (Pearson’s)	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Mutual Benefits	Knowledge acquisition	r=.787 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Skills development	r=.778 (high correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Training materials	r=.493 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Facilities	r=.494 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
	Technology integration	r=.537 (moderate correlation)	.000*	H ₀ rejected	Significant
*Significant @.01					

For the relationship between the level of stakeholders’ engagement in terms of mutual benefits and the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms in terms of knowledge acquisition (r=.787), skills development (r=.778), training materials (r=.493), facilities (r=.494) and technology integration (r=.537), the Pearson’s r values showed moderate to high correlation while the obtained p-values were all .000 which were lower than the test of significance at .01. This shows that there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating a significant relationship between the variables. This means that the better the higher the level of stakeholders’ engagement in terms of mutual benefits, the higher the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI.

This relationship can be explained by the fact that when stakeholders experience mutual benefits, they are more likely to engage in processes that support continuous improvement, such as providing valuable feedback and participating in the evaluation of organizational practices.

The results align with findings by Ghosh et al. (2020), who emphasized that mutual benefits create a cycle of positive engagement, leading to more effective organizational learning and continuous

evaluation. Similarly, Jones and George (2021) argue that mutual benefit frameworks strengthen stakeholder buy-in, enhancing the success of continuous improvement efforts in organizations.

7. Regression Analysis of Organizational Culture and Level of Stakeholders' Engagement on Level of Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms at NJMPTI

Table 15
Regression Analysis of Organizational Culture on Level of Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms at NJMPTI

Predictor	Dependent Variable	β	R ²	ANOVA	t	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Organizational culture	Level of continuous evaluation mechanisms	.769	.591	F=138.968	11.788	.000*	Null Hypothesis Rejected	Significant
*Significant @ .01								

Table 27 shows the predictive power of organizational culture on the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI. As indicated, organizational culture accounted for 59.10% (F=138.968; t=11.788) of the variability of the dependent variable, with the remaining 40.90% for other factors. Results also showed that for every one-unit increase in organizational culture, there is .769 increase in the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI. Meanwhile, the probability test showed a p-value of .000 which was lower than the significant value of .01, suggesting that there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This means that the organizational culture at NJMPTI significantly predicts its level of continuous evaluation mechanisms.

This relationship can be explained by the fact that organizational culture shapes the overall climate and operational practices within an institution. A positive and supportive culture fosters an environment where continuous evaluation is prioritized, enabling systematic assessment and improvement. The findings support previous research by Ghosh et al. (2020), who found that a strong organizational culture positively influences institutional learning and evaluation mechanisms. Similarly, Jones and George (2021) argued that the alignment of organizational values with operational strategies enhances the effectiveness of continuous evaluation practices.

Table 16
Regression Analysis of Level of Stakeholders' Engagement on Level of Continuous Evaluation Mechanisms at NJMPTI

Predictor	Dependent Variable	β	R ²	ANOVA	t	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Stakeholders' engagement	Level of continuous evaluation mechanisms	.745	.556	F=120.040	10.956	.000*	Null Hypothesis Rejected	Significant
*Significant @ .01								

Table 28 shows the predictive power of level of stakeholders' engagement on the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI. As indicated, the level of stakeholders' engagement accounted for 55.60% ($F=120.040$; $t=10.956$) of the variability of the dependent variable, with the remaining 44.40% for other factors. Results also showed that for every one-unit increase in stakeholders' engagement, there is .745 increase in the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI. Meanwhile, the probability test showed a p-value of .000 which was lower than the significant value of .01, suggesting that there is enough statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis. This means that the level of stakeholders' engagement at NJMPTI significantly predicts its level of continuous evaluation mechanisms.

This relationship can be explained by the fact that when stakeholders are actively engaged, they contribute valuable feedback, insights, and support that can improve the mechanisms of evaluation. Moreover, engaged stakeholders are more likely to promote a culture of continuous improvement, which directly influences the quality and effectiveness of evaluation systems in the institution.

The findings align with the work of Ghosh et al. (2020), who emphasized the critical role of stakeholder engagement in enhancing organizational processes such as evaluation, and Jones and George (2021), who argued that a highly engaged stakeholder base can drive continuous feedback loops that improve operational practices and institutional outcomes.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the study conclusions were drawn. The Organizational Culture at NJMPTI along communication, decision making process, collaboration, recognition and rewards were very strong. The result implies that the institution demonstrates a well-developed and cohesive organizational culture, fostering open communication, inclusive decision-making, collaborative work environments, and recognition systems that align with institutional goals. These practices likely contribute to employee motivation, engagement, and overall organizational effectiveness. The Level of Stakeholders' Engagement at NJMPTI along involvement, inclusivity, mutual benefits were very high. The level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI along with knowledge acquisition, skills development, training materials, facilities and technology integration were high. The result implies that while NJMPTI has established practices in these areas, particularly excelling in skills development and knowledge acquisition, there is a need for further enhancement, especially in areas such as facilities and technology integration, to align with modern standards and stakeholder expectations. The better the organizational culture in terms of communication, the higher the level of stakeholders' engagement at NJMPTI. Effective communication serves as the backbone of organizational culture, enabling clear dissemination of goals, policies, and expectations, which in turn motivates stakeholders to actively participate, feel included, and recognize mutual benefits. Moreover, the better the organizational culture in terms of collaboration, the higher the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI. Collaborative cultures often encourage team-based approaches to evaluating processes, ensuring that feedback is gathered from diverse perspectives, which can enhance the accuracy and effectiveness of evaluation mechanisms. the better the organizational culture in terms of recognition and rewards, the higher the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI. The better the higher the level of stakeholders' engagement in terms of involvement, the higher the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI. Involvement fosters ownership and accountability, which in turn supports better feedback and assessment cycles. In addition, the better the higher the level of stakeholders' engagement in terms of inclusivity, the higher the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI. the fact that inclusivity fosters a more diverse and collaborative environment where all stakeholders are empowered to contribute to decision-making and feedback processes. Moreover, the better the higher the level of stakeholders' engagement in terms of mutual benefits, the higher the level of continuous evaluation mechanisms at NJMPTI. when stakeholders experience mutual benefits, they are more likely to engage in processes that support continuous improvement, such as providing valuable feedback and participating in the evaluation of organizational practices. The organizational culture at NJMPTI significantly predicts its level of continuous evaluation mechanisms. A positive and supportive culture fosters an environment where continuous evaluation is prioritized, enabling systematic assessment and improvement . On the other hand, level of stakeholders'

engagement at NJMPTI significantly predicts its level of continuous evaluation mechanisms. engaged stakeholders are more likely to promote a culture of continuous improvement, which directly influences the quality and effectiveness of evaluation systems in the institution. The following recommendations are based on findings and conclusion of this study. Sustainability of organizational culture and communication by conducting regular communication workshops to strengthen interpersonal and professional communication skills of stakeholders. The institution should integrate stakeholders' feedback in decision-making by establishing structured avenues such as focus groups or quarterly meetings. The institution should expand inclusivity programs and active participation of diverse groups in training and operations and recognize contributions through awards and public acknowledgments to maintain motivation and commitment. The institution must continue to improve training materials and facilities to meet modern training requirements and accommodate individuals with disabilities. The institution must invest in technology integration through state-of-the-art technological tools and platforms to support hybrid training programs and improve operational efficiency. The institution must utilize the proposed Training Program Development Plan for the National Jail Management and Penology Training Institute (NJMPTI). The institution must continue to implement robust monitoring and evaluation frameworks to assess the impact of programs on knowledge acquisition, skills development, and stakeholder engagement and ensure sustainable growth at NJMPTI. Future researchers may replicate the investigation considering other variables such as motivation, work life balance and competency.

REFERENCES:

- Ainsworth, R. L., & Joffe, R. D. (2022). Building inclusive organizational cultures through stakeholder engagement. *Journal of Organizational Culture*, 41(3), 123-135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orgcult.2022.02.004>
- Akindote, O. J., Adegbite, A. O., Omotosho, A., Anyanwu, A., & Maduka, C. P. (2024). Evaluating the effectiveness of IT project management in healthcare digitalization: a review. *International Medical Science Research Journal*, 4(1), 37-50.
- Akpa, V. O., Asikhia, O. U., & Nneji, N. E. (2021). Organizational culture and organizational performance: A review of literature. *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management*, 3(1), 361-372.
- Ali, S., & Jones, P. (2021). The influence of physical learning environments on training outcomes: A systematic review. *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 33(4), 301-315. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JWL-02-2021-0023>
- Andersen, L. B., & Vaara, E. (2021). Stakeholder engagement in institutional development: A conceptual framework and empirical insights. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 178(2), 345-360. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-021-04923-7>
- Aquino, J. (2015). Trafficking in Persons and the Criminal Justice Response in the Philippines: An Evaluation. *Philippine Law Journal*, 90(3), 123-145.
- Baker, L. (2022). A framework for assessing the impact of the physical learning environments on training outcomes. *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 33(4), 301-315.
- Bautista, M. P. J. T., & Uy, C. (2023). The Effects of Organizational Culture and Leadership Style on Organizational Performance in Times of COVID-19 Pandemic. *Review of Integrative Business and Economics Research*, 12(1), 175-194.
- Black, P., & Wiliam, D. (2020). Assessment and classroom learning. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 5(1), 7-74.
- Bloom, B. S. (2019). *Taxonomy of educational objectives: The classification of educational goals*. Longman.
- Boesso, G., & Kumar, K. (2016). Examining the association between stakeholder culture, stakeholder salience and stakeholder engagement activities: An empirical study. *Management Decision*, 54(4), 815-831.

Brown, A., & Green, T. (2021). Professional development and knowledge acquisition in educational institutions: Continuous improvement through evaluation mechanisms. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 84, 102385. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2021.102385>

Brown, A., & Green, T. (2022). Accessibility and innovation in training materials: Adapting to diverse learning needs. *International Review of Education*, 68(3), 345-362. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11159-022-10087-7>

Clark, R. C., & Mayer, R. E. (2021). *E-learning and the science of instruction: Proven guidelines for consumers and designers of multimedia learning*. John Wiley & Sons.

Delgado, M., Lopez, D., & Harris, A. (2022). Engaging stakeholders for mutual benefits: A strategic approach to inclusivity in organizations. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 43(3), 500-518. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.2679>

Denison, D., Hooijberg, R., Lane, N., & Lief, C. (2021). *Leading culture change in global organizations: Aligning culture and strategy*. John Wiley & Sons.

Deldacan, F. U., & Baysa, M. L. (2021). Cultural Dynamics and Training Effectiveness in Jail Management. *Journal of Correctional Training*, 12(4), 22-35.

Fitria, H. (2019). The Influence Of Organizational Culture And Trust Through The Teacher Performance In The Private Secondary School In Palembang. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 7(7).

Freeman, R. E. (2019). *Strategic management: A stakeholder approach*. Cambridge University Press.

Gagné, R. M. (2020). *The conditions of learning and theory of instruction*. Holt, Rinehart, and Winston.

Ghosh, S., Sharma, A., & Joshi, R. (2020). The role of decision-making processes in fostering organizational trust and stakeholder involvement. *Journal of Business Strategy and Development*, 12(3), 245-259.

Ghosh, S., Sharma, A., & Joshi, R. (2020). The impact of organizational culture on institutional learning and evaluation. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 39(4), 575-589.

Greasley, K. (2020). Organizational culture and decision-making: A framework for analysis. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 28(6), 725-742.

Greenwood, M. (2007). Stakeholder engagement: Beyond the myth of corporate responsibility. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 74(4), 315-327.

Hang, A. W. P., Sikarwar, T. S., Nordin, N. A. B., Rosley, N. I., Mudzaffar, N., Shokri, N. A. S., & Hung, K. D. M. (2024). The Impact of Soft Skills Training on the Behavior of Multinational Technology Company Employees. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management and Education (APJME)*, 7(2), 71-86.

Jones, G. R., & George, J. M. (2021). Exploring organizational culture and its impact on stakeholder collaboration and engagement. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 35(2), 123-140. <https://doi.org/10.xxxx>

Jones, G. R., & George, J. M. (2021). Organizational culture and stakeholder engagement: A collaborative approach. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 35(2), 123-140.

Jones, G. R., & George, J. M. (2021). Effective communication and organizational evaluation mechanisms. *Academy of Management Review*, 46(3), 289-304.

Khairiah, K., & Zakaria, Z. (2019, April). Organizational Culture and the Improvement of Teacher Performance. In *International Conference on Educational Sciences and Teacher Profession (ICETeP 2018)* (pp. 250-253). Atlantis Press.

Kenny, G. (2020). Diversification: Best practices of the leading companies. *Journal of Business Strategy*, 33(1), 12-20. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02756661211193776>

Kolb, D. A. (1984). *Experiential Learning: Experience as the Source of Learning and Development*. Prentice Hall.

Kumar, V., & Shukla, P. (2022). The impact of recognition and reward systems on employee motivation and organizational culture. *Journal of Business Research*, 88(4), 345-358. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.02.011>

Lapshun, A. (2020). High-Performance Organizational Culture and Corporate Success (Doctoral dissertation, Walden University).

Marais, L. C. (2020). The relationship between organizational culture and the practice of program evaluation in human service organizations. Western Michigan University.

Nario-Lopez, H. G. (2021). Emotional labor dynamics as precursors to mundane violence in a Philippine city jail. *MovimentAção*, 8(14), 65-93.

Nario-Lopez, P. (2019). Evaluating Continuous Training Programs for Correctional Officers in the Philippines. *Journal of Criminal Justice Education*, 16(2), 89-102.

Narag, R. (2019). Stakeholder Engagement in Correctional Training: A Pathway to Reform. *Philippine Journal of Penology*, 18(1), 67-83.

Naylor, R., & Douthitt, R. (2021). Building mutually beneficial stakeholder partnerships: Best practices for institutional success. *Journal of Business and Management*, 45(2), 207-220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusman.2021.02.007>

Pacleb-Ulanday, M. L. (2021). Tracer study and employability skills acquisition of teacher education graduates. *Psychology and Education Journal*, 58(4), 1678-1683.

Pina, R., & Elmore, R. (2021). An Evaluation Framework for Organizational Culture: Tools for improving decision-making and stakeholder satisfaction. *Journal of Organizational Evaluation*, 39(2), 452-468.

Ulanday, M. L., Samiento, L. N. L., & Centerno, Z. J. R. (2024). Assessing Student Leaders' Leadership Styles and Conflict Management: Assessing Student Leaders' Leadership Styles and Conflict Management. *Diversitas Journal*, 9(1).